

23rd EVER Congress

Valencia
13-15 October
2022

CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE

This is to certify that

Omar Saoud

attended the

23rd EVER Congress

October 13th - 15th, 2022
Valencia, Spain

The President

Professor Manuel Vidal Sanz

oic
meeting
specialists